

**Low Cytotoxicity, Antibacterial Property, and Curcumin Delivery
Performance of Toughness-Enhanced Electrospun Composite Membranes
Based on Poly(lactic acid) and MAX Phase (Ti₃AlC₂)**

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Abstract

MXenes, synthesized from their precursor MAX phases, have been extensively researched as additives to enhance the drug delivery performance of polymer matrices, whereas there is a limited number of previous reports on the use of MAX phases themselves for such applications. The use of MAX phases can exclude the complicated synthesis procedure and lessen resultant production and environmental costs required to convert MAX phases to MXenes. Herein, electrospun membranes of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) and a MAX phase (Ti_3AlC_2) have been fabricated for curcumin delivery. The composite membrane exhibits significantly higher toughness (8.82 MJ m^{-3}) than the plasticized PLA membrane (0.63 MJ m^{-3}) with low cytotoxicity, supporting proliferation of mouse fibroblast L929 cells. The curcumin-loaded composite membrane exhibits high water vapor transmission ($\sim 7350 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$), porosity ($\sim 85 \%$), water wettability, and antibacterial properties against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Seven-day curcumin release is enhanced from 45 % (PLA) to 67 % (composite) due to curcumin diffusion from the polymer fibers and MAX phase surface that contributes to overall increased curcumin adsorption and release sites. This work demonstrates the potential of the MAX phase to enhance both properties and curcumin delivery, promising for other eco-friendly systems for sustainable drug delivery applications.

Keywords: Poly(lactic acid), MAX phase, Electrospun membrane, Drug delivery, Curcumin, Low cytotoxicity

1. Introduction

The repair of wounds of varied thickness and intensity is a common process that is often faced in our daily lives. Wound healing occurs in three stages: inflammation, proliferation, and maturation. While dealing with various forms of skin injury or burns, it is vital to cure the wounds as quickly as possible and in line with expert wound care advice. Wound dressings have been developed to preserve injured skin by being applied to wounds [1]. An optimal wound dressing should be able to retain moisture, protect tissue from various forms of injury, be antimicrobial, and possess acceptable mechanical and physicochemical characteristics [2]. Moreover, wound dressings should be biocompatible, readily removed after use and, ideally, biodegradable [1].

Curcumin (Cur), also known as [1,7-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-1,6-heptadien-2,5-dione][3], is a natural polyphenol that is derived from turmeric [3-7]. The primary benefits of Cur include its antioxidative, antibacterial, antiviral, anti-cancer, and anti-inflammatory properties [5,6,8,9]. Moreover, Cur has been studied as a model drug in biomedical applications by being loaded into polymeric materials, including poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) [8,9], polycaprolactone [5,8], polyurethane [8], poly(vinyl alcohol) [4], chitosan [6], and poly(lactic acid) (PLA) [3,9]. With increasing concern of environmental sustainability, PLA is applied in the present work due to its non-toxicity, compostability, biodegradability, and compliance with sustainable development goals [3,10-12]. As a green, degradable, and recyclable polymeric material, PLA can be made from agricultural waste, while its use involves low CO₂ emission. Use of biodegradable PLA promotes a reduction in plastic waste disposal and incineration [12]. PLA is additionally a commercial polymer widely used in medical implants, tissue culture, restorable surgical sutures, wound closure, and controlled release systems [11]. Due to the hydrophobic nature of PLA, it can be used as a carrier for Cur, which is a hydrophobic drug [10]. However, the hydrophobicity of PLA does

not facilitate water vapor transmission from the wound outward to the air interface. PEG was thus utilized as an additive to PLA to increase the hydrophilicity of the developed material. Importantly, it has been previously reported that PEG is a biocompatible hydrophilic polymer and, hence, it offers significant promise in biomedical applications [10].

The mechanical robustness of materials used in wound dressings should be considered in relation to its use adjacent to human skin movement. One approach for increasing the strength is to incorporate micro- or nanomaterials into the polymeric matrix for reinforcing purposes. There are several materials that can be used as polymer additives, such as graphene oxide [13,14], titanium dioxide [15], mesoporous silica nanoparticles [16] and their modified form [17], halloysite nanotubes [18], and MXene (Ti_3C_2) [19]. At present, MXene has attracted much attention owing to its multifunctional performance and biocompatibility, leading also to research and development in MAX phases, which are precursors to MXenes [19-22]. A MAX phase is a layered ternary carbide with the chemical structure $\text{M}_{n+1}\text{AX}_n$, where M is a transition metal, A is silicon or aluminum, X is nitrogen or carbon, and $n = 1, 2, \text{ or } 3$ [23]. Titanium aluminum carbide (Ti_3AlC_2) is a MAX phase family that has been extensively researched in a variety of applications because of its high elasticity, large surface area, and excellent electrical conductivity [24]. Utilizing a MAX phase can be a route to a reduction of the complex synthesis process required for MXene production, thereby leading to a relatively lower production cost of final composite materials. However, published literature relating to MAX phases for biomedical applications is limited [25-29]. It has been reported that an optimal concentration of MAX phase is required for cell viability as a high MAX phase concentration ($\geq 400 \mu\text{g/mL}$) can result in cytotoxicity [26]. In other previous reports, composites of Ti_2AlN MAX phase were applied in biomedical applications for bone regeneration purposes with cytocompatibility [27-29]. However, these findings were not

related to drug delivery applications. Upon the controversial and diverging hypotheses regarding the cytotoxicity of MAX phases, polymer/MAX phase composites have not been reported for drug release technologies.

Electrospinning was adopted to fabricate Cur carriers in this work because the electrospun membranes typically comprise polymer fiber sizes ranging in the nanoscale to the microscale. Membranes with such fine polymer fibers possess a high surface area, thereby benefiting a large number of Cur delivery sites. When being used as a component in a wound dressing pad, the porous structure of the electrospun membranes also allows for “breathing” of the wound underneath the membrane.

PLA, as a green polymer in compliance with sustainable development, was electrospun herein to fabricate fibrous membranes for use as scaffolds that are capable of delivering Cur with antibacterial property. The MAX phase of Ti_3AlC_2 was incorporated into PEG-plasticized PLA membranes to explore the potential of the MAX phase in enhancing the Cur-delivery ability of the polymer membranes. Being used as an additive of the PLA-based matrix, the MAX phase was loaded into the PLA membrane matrix at low concentrations. Finally, the effects of the MAX phase on cytotoxicity of the composite membrane are presented to pave the way for practical utilization of MAX phase in tissue engineering and biomedical applications.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA, 2003D grade, weight-average molecular weight ~ 207 kDa, and number-average molecular weight ~ 96 kDa) pellets were purchased from NatureWorks LLC, USA. Poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG400, molecular weight = 405 g mol^{-1}) was purchased from NOF

Co., Ltd., Japan. Titanium aluminum carbide (MAX phase, Ti_3AlC_2 , 98 % purity, relative molar mass = $194.605 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) was supplied by American Elements, USA. Chloroform (99.8 % assay), dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.8 % assay), and ethanol (99.7 %) were obtained from RCI Labscan, Thailand. Curcumin (Cur, ≥ 65 % analyzed by HPLC, relative molar mass = $368.38 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. Phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH = 7.4) tablets were purchased from EMD Millipore Corp., USA.

2.2 Preparation of PLA membrane and PLA/MAX phase membrane

PLA membranes were prepared by initially dissolving PLA to prepare 8, 10, 12, and 14 wt% solutions in chloroform:DMF (90:10 % v/v) with magnetic stirring. A fibrous membrane was fabricated by electrospinning from a 5 mL glass syringe with a constant tip-to-collector distance of 20 cm, metal needle inner diameter of 0.8 mm, and applied voltage of 20 or 25 kV.

To prepare PLA/MAX phase composite membranes, MAX phase particles were firstly dispersed at 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 3.00, and 5.00 parts per hundred resin (phr), relative to the PLA weight, in the mixed solvent used for PLA membrane fabrication. The dispersion was made homogeneous by ultrasonication using a Vibra-Cell VCX130 (USA). PLA pellets were subsequently dissolved in the obtained MAX phase dispersion by stirring prior to electrospinning. The PLA/MAX phase composite membrane is referred to as 'PMX membrane'.

2.3 Preparation of plasticized PLA membranes and plasticized PLA/MAX phase membranes

To prepare plasticized PLA membranes, PLA (14 wt%) and PEG (3 wt%) were dissolved in the mixed solvent by stirring. Plasticized PLA membranes, named 'PE membranes', were then prepared by electrospinning.

Composite membranes of plasticized PLA/MAX phase were fabricated initially by dispersing MAX phase particles (for instance, 1 phr relative to PLA weight) with PEG solution by ultrasonication before electrospinning process. The obtained composite membranes are referred to as 'PE1MX membranes', where 1 denotes 1 phr.

2.4 Preparation of Cur-loaded plasticized PLA membranes and Cur-loaded plasticized PLA/MAX phase membranes

For a comparison in Cur-release performance of the PLA-based membranes, Cur-loaded MAX phase (MX/Cur) was also prepared by ultrasonication of MAX phase in a dispersion of Cur particles in a chloroform:DMF (90:10 % v/v) mixed solvent, followed by drying.

Cur (10 phr relative to PLA) was dispersed in the chloroform:DMF (90:10 % v/v) mixed solvent by ultrasonication. PLA (12 wt%) and PEG (3 wt%) were dissolved in the previously prepared Cur dispersion and subjected to electrospinning. The prepared membranes are referred to as 'PEC membranes'.

For the Cur-loaded plasticized PLA/MAX phase membranes (PEMXC), Cur (10 phr) was dispersed in the mixed solvent with various MAX phase loadings (0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 3.00, and 5.00 phr relative to the PLA weight used). PLA and PEG were dissolved in a dispersion of Cur and MAX phase before electrospinning. The prepared membranes were named PE0.25MXC, PE0.5MXC, PE0.75MXC, PE1MXC, PE3MXC, and PE5MXC membrane, respectively. Compositions of all membrane formulations in this work are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Formulations of the membranes prepared in the present work.

Membrane	Composition			
	PLA (wt%)	PEG (wt%)	MAX phase (phr)	Curcumin (phr)
PLA	12	-	-	-
PC	12	-	-	10
P1MX	12	-	1	-
PE	12	3	-	-
PEC	12	3	-	10
PE1MX	12	3	1	-
PE1MXC	12	3	1	10

2.5 Characterization

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed on a JSM-IT300 (JEOL, Japan) to investigate the morphology of MAX phase, Cur, and Cur-immobilized MAX phase. Each sample was attached to an SEM stub using copper tape. For electrospun membranes of PLA, PMX, PE, PEMX, PEC, and PEMXC, each membrane was cut into small pieces and attached to the SEM stub using carbon tape. Gold sputtering was applied to coat all samples before SEM observation.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was investigated using a JEM 2010 instrument (JEOL, Japan) at 200 kV and 80 kV accelerating voltages for the MAX phase and PE1MX membrane, respectively.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of MAX phase and membranes of PLA, PE, and PE1MX were obtained using a Rigaku SmartLab (Rigaku, Japan) X-ray diffractometer with a Cu-K α X-ray source ($\lambda = 1.54059$ nm). Each sample was scanned to collect data from 2θ range of 5 to 60°.

Raman spectroscopy was studied using a Bruker Senterra dispersive Raman spectrometer (Bruker, Germany) to record the Raman spectrum of MAX phase using an excitation laser wavelength of 532 nm, laser power of 12.5 mW, and a Raman shift range of 100–1400 cm $^{-1}$.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of PLA, PE, and PE1MX membranes were obtained using an attenuated total reflectance-Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (Bruker, Germany).

Mechanical properties of PLA-based membranes were determined under tension. PLA, PE, and PE1MX membranes were cut into small pieces, each with a size of 1 \times 7 cm 2 and thickness of 0.1755 \pm 0.0267 cm (PLA), 0.2548 \pm 0.0995 cm (PE), and 0.3717 \pm 0.0702 cm (PE1MX). Mechanical testing was performed using an LRX (Lloyd, UK) tensile testing machine with a gauge length of 5 cm, preload of 0.0100 N, and tensile speed of 10.00 mm min $^{-1}$. At least five specimens were tested for each type of membrane. Young's modulus of each membrane was obtained from a slope of a stress-strain curve in the elastic linear portion, which was the initial region of the curve.

Thermal properties of PLA, PE, and PE1MX membranes were studied by means of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using a DSC 7 (Perkin Elmer, USA) with a temperature range of 0–200 °C and a heating rate of 10 °C min $^{-1}$. Thermal stability was investigated through determining the decomposition temperature of PE and PE1MX membranes by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Each sample was placed in an alumina pan prior to measurement using a Thermo plus EVO2 simultaneous thermal analyzer (Rigaku, Japan). The data were collected with a heating rate of 10 °C min $^{-1}$ in a temperature range of 30–430 °C under a nitrogen gas atmosphere.

Chemical bonds and elements within samples were analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). An AXIS Ultra DLD spectrometer (Kratos Analytical Ltd., UK) was operated and the data were reported as binding energy of MAX phase and Cur-immobilized MAX phase.

PC, PEC, and P1MXC membranes were cut into pieces of $0.5 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$ each and placed on a microscope slide. The hydrophilicity of the membrane sample was investigated using an SL200KB contact angle meter (Kino Scientific Instrument Inc., USA) with the Young-Laplace equation fitting method. Deionized water ($5 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$) was applied for each measurement. The measurement was performed in triplicate to obtain an average water contact angle value.

Water vapor transmission rates (WVTRs) of PEC and PE1MXC membranes were measured according to ASTM E96/E96M-16 (Standard Test Method for Water Vapor Transmission of Materials). Each membrane was cut into a $15 \times 15 \text{ cm}^2$ piece and tested using a W3/031 water vapor transmission rate tester (Labthink Instruments Co., Ltd., USA) at $38 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 90 % relative humidity.

Porosities of PEC and PE1MXC electrospun membranes were calculated according to Eq. (1) [30]:

$$Porosity = \left[V - \frac{\rho_{membrane}}{\rho_{bulk}} \right] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where $V (\text{m}^3)$ is the volume of the membrane, $\rho_{membrane}$ is the density of the membrane calculated by measuring its dimensions, and ρ_{bulk} is the density of bulk PEC and PE1MXC films measured using a Radwag KIT 85 density determination kit with an AS 3100.X2 PLUS analytical balance (Radwag, Poland).

Staphylococcus aureus (*S. aureus*) and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) were used as gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, respectively, in antibacterial activity tests. Five pieces of each membrane type and 10^8 CFU mL^{-1} ($\text{OD}_{600 \text{ nm}} = 0.08\text{--}0.1$) bacteria were incubated at $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 0,

12, 24, and 168 h. The number of bacteria was counted in colony forming unit by dilution spread plate. Results were compared between the fabricated PEC and PE1MXC membranes, with untreated control (bacterial control, which was bacteria and their food without the test with membrane samples).

2.6 Cytotoxicity

For the *in vitro* direct method, 1×10^4 mouse fibroblast cells (L929 cells) were placed on the PE and PE1MX membranes in a 24-well plate. Samples were incubated at 37 ± 1 °C with 5 ± 0.1 % CO₂ and 95 ± 5 % relative humidity for 7 days. The samples were then fixed in a fixation solution, rinsed in washing solution, and kept overnight. Samples were subsequently dehydrated by immersing them in ethanol with increasing concentration of 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 %v/v for 15 minutes at each concentration. Before being examined by SEM, the samples were sputter-coated with gold. Polyurethane film with 0.1 % zinc diethyldithiocarbamate (ZDEC):RM-A and Thermanox (Nunc) coverslip served as positive and negative controls, respectively.

Cell viability was investigated by seeding 1×10^5 cells mL⁻¹ (L929 cells) in MEM complete medium into the 96-well plate for 24 ± 2 h and incubated at 37 ± 1 °C with CO₂ and relative humidity controlled at 5 ± 0.1 % and 95 ± 5 %, respectively. The MEM complete medium was then replaced with the extracts of different samples: the blank (the media without test specimen), negative control (Thermanox (Nunc) coverslip), positive control (polyurethane film containing 0.1 % zinc diethyldithiocarbamate (ZDEC):RM-A), and test specimens (surface area-to-volume extraction ratio of 3 cm² mL⁻¹). All samples were extracted for 24 h at 37 ± 1 °C. The cells were incubated for 24 ± 2 and 72 ± 2 h before being dyed with MTT (3-(4,5-dimethyl thiosol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) and incubated further for 2 h to completely dry the samples.

Subsequently, the MTT was removed and DMSO was added to each well. Finally, light absorbance at 570 nm was measured using a microplate reader. A similar procedure of the *in vitro* indirect method was performed for the positive and negative control. The cytotoxicity tests were performed in triplicate.

2.7 *In vitro* Cur release

PEC and various PEMXC membranes were cut into $3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$ pieces and then immersed in 50 mL of 10% v/v ethanol in PBS (pH 7.4) [31]. The sample bottles were shaken in a DIS-20 shaker incubator (Taisite Lab Sciences, Inc., USA) at 37 °C [8,32] and 100 rpm [8]. At 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3, 6, 12, 24, 36, 48, 72, 120, and 168 h, 5 mL of the PBS solution containing released Cur was taken at each time and replaced with fresh PBS solution. The concentration of Cur was determined by means of measuring light absorbance for the Cur-release medium at 424 nm using an Evolution 201 UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, Massachusetts, USA). The procedure for Cur-release study of Cur-loaded MAX phase (MX/Cur) was similar to that used for the PLA-based membranes. Each data point of the Cur-release percentage was averaged from the measurements performed in triplicate.

The Cur-release data were fitted with five kinetic models, including zero-order, first-order, Hixon-Crowell, Korsmeyer-Peppas, and Higuchi model [33], according to Eq. (2-6):

$$\text{Zero-order model:} \quad Q_t = Q_0 + K_z t \quad (2)$$

$$\text{First-order model:} \quad \ln Q_t = \ln Q_0 + K_f t \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Hixon-Crowell model:} \quad Q_0^{1/3} - Q_t^{1/3} = K_{HC} t \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Korsmeyer-Peppas model:} \quad Q_t/Q_\infty = K_{KP} t^n \quad (5)$$

Higuchi model:
$$Q_t = K_H t^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where Q_0 , Q_t , and Q_∞ are the initial amount of Cur before release, the amount of Cur released at time t , and the total amount of drug dissolved, respectively. K_z , K_f , K_{HC} , K_{KP} , and K_H are the Cur-release rate constants for the zero-order, first-order, Hixon-Crowell, Korsmeyer-Peppas, and Higuchi model, respectively.

2.8 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using ANOVA followed by a post hoc test ($p < 0.05$).

3. Results and discussion

MAX phase was characterized by TEM, HR-TEM, SEM, EDS analysis, XRD, and Raman spectroscopy. The characterization results (Fig. S1 and Fig. S2) and discussion are provided in the Supplementary Material.

3.1 Determination of optimal conditions for electrospinning PLA membranes

PLA concentration (8, 10, 12, and 14 wt% solutions in 90:10 % v/v chloroform:DMF) and applied voltage (20 and 25 kV) were varied to determine the optimal conditions for electrospinning. SEM images (Fig. 1a-h) show that increasing the PLA concentration and applied voltage resulted in continuous bead-free PLA fibers. A PLA concentration of 14 wt% and applied voltage of 25 kV were thus selected as the conditions for electrospinning composite membranes throughout this work since membranes with fibrous morphology was clearly observed under these particular conditions. At low PLA concentration (8 and 10 wt%), beaded fibers were found in the PLA membranes since the PLA concentrations were not high enough to allow for PLA chain entanglement. Consequently, the PLA solution could not be continuously stretched to form long fibers after solvent evaporation. At each PLA concentration used, the higher applied voltage (25

kV) contributed to more stretching of the PLA solution, compared to the use of lower applied voltage (20 kV). However, PLA concentrations higher than 14 wt% were not applied herein due to significantly high PLA solution viscosity that restricted PLA solution stretching between the syringe needle and collector.

Fig. 1. (a)-(h) SEM images of PLA membranes electrospun using different PLA solution concentrations and applied voltages.

3.2 Preparation of plasticized PLA/MAX phase electrospun composite membranes (PEMX)

Different MAX phase contents (0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 3, and 5 phr) were loaded into the PLA solution for electrospinning PMX composite membranes. SEM images (Fig. 2a-f) show that beaded fibers were produced at low MAX phase loadings (0.25, 0.5, and 0.75, Fig. 2a-c). Fibrous morphologies were more evident with higher MAX phase loadings (1, 3, and 5 phr, Fig. 2d-f) due to increased conductivity of the electrospinning solution [34]. The increase in electrical conductivity was a contribution from the excellent electrical conductivity of MAX phase [24]. For a solution containing both MAX phase and a polymer, the presence of MAX phase can increase the overall electrical conductivity of the solution. The increased electrical charges on the surface of polymer

jet thus facilitated fiber formation under the electric field during electrospinning. In this work, a MAX phase content of 1 phr was selected for further membrane preparation and characterization due to the highest performance of PE1MXC membrane in releasing Cur, as compared to other plasticized PLA and composite membranes (shown in Section 3.8). Moreover, the lowest loading of MAX phase that produced fibers (1 phr) was also selected instead of 3 and 5 phr since a low loading reduces production costs, and does not cause significant cytotoxicity (shown in Section 3.4).

Fig. 2. SEM images of PMX phase composite membranes containing different MAX phase loadings: (a) 0.25, (b) 0.5, (c) 0.75, (d) 1, (e) 3, and (f) 5 phr.

PEG was incorporated into the PLA and PMX composite membranes to increase their hydrophilicity and facilitate Cur release in aqueous PBS solutions. It was found that the presence of PEG in the PE membrane (Fig. 3a) and PE1MX membrane (Fig. 3b) did not destroy the fiber integrity of the membranes. The TEM image (Fig. 3c) of the PE1MX membrane indicates that the

MAX phase particle protruded from either side of the polymer fiber, contributing to extra surface area of the composite membrane for Cur adsorption and release. Compared to the average fiber size ($2.81 \pm 1.96 \mu\text{m}$, Fig 3d) found within PLA membranes (Fig. 1h), the average fiber diameters of the PE membrane ($1.85 \pm 0.82 \mu\text{m}$, Fig. 3e) and the PE1MX membrane ($1.27 \pm 0.41 \mu\text{m}$, Fig. 3f) were smaller. It can thus be inferred that the presence of MAX phase in the PLA solution contributed to the formation of homogeneously fine PLA fibers (Fig. 3b) due to increased conductivity of the polymer solution. Cur release could be retarded by the polymer molecules when diffusing from the bulk or thicker fibers as compared to the Cur diffusion out of thinner fibers, thus it is speculated that these thinner fibers will be beneficial for rapid Cur release. In addition, most of the MAX phase particles are likely to protrude from the small PLA fibers, enabling better Cur adsorption and subsequent release.

Fig. 3. SEM images of plasticized PLA-based membranes: (a) PE and (b) PE1MX membranes. (c) TEM image of a PE1MX membrane. Fiber diameter and fiber size distribution of (d) PLA, (e) PE, and (f) PE1MX membranes ($n = 100$).

3.3 Characterization of plasticized PLA membranes (PE) and plasticized PLA/MAX phase membranes (PE1MX)

FTIR spectra show the presence of PEG in PE and PE1MX composite membranes (Fig. 4a). As shown by the dashed lines in Fig. 4a, PEG characteristic bands were observed in PE and PE1MX membranes at ~ 950 , ~ 2870 , and ~ 3420 cm^{-1} , representing the vibration of $-\text{CH}$ bending, $-\text{CH}_3$ stretching, and $\text{O}-\text{H}$ stretching, respectively [35]. PLA characteristic bands were observed at ~ 755 and ~ 870 cm^{-1} for the crystalline and amorphous regions, respectively [35]. Stretching vibrations of PLA were detected at ~ 1085 and ~ 1182 cm^{-1} for $\text{C}-\text{O}$, and ~ 1755 cm^{-1} for $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching [36]. Bending vibrations in PLA were observed at ~ 1358 cm^{-1} for symmetric $-\text{CH}_3$ and ~ 1450 cm^{-1} for asymmetric $-\text{CH}_3$ [36]. Since no peaks formed or disappeared from the FTIR spectrum of PLA, it is assumed that there was no significant chemical interaction between PLA and PEG in the PE and PE1MX composite membranes. Moreover, no significant changes were detected between the FTIR spectra of PE and PE1MX membranes, reflecting that the MAX phase did not form strong interactions with the polymer matrix.

Fig. 4. Characteristics of PLA, PE, and PE1MX membranes: (a) FTIR spectra and (b) XRD patterns.

XRD was used to investigate the crystallographic structure of PLA-based membranes (Fig. 4b). The XRD patterns of PE and PE1MX membranes show the characteristic peaks for PLA at 2θ of 16.5° and for PEG at 18.8° and 22.2° [37-41], indicating that the incorporation of PEG into the PLA electrospun membrane facilitated PLA crystal formation. Such a finding of PEG-enhanced PLA crystal formation is consistent to a previous report [37]. It was earlier shown that increasing PEG content resulted in a more intense XRD peak of PLA since PEG molecules facilitate the PLA chain mobility and result in ordered chain arrangement. However, when the PEG loading was high, the XRD peak of PLA was less intense due to the formation of PEG crystals that restricted PLA chain packing. Herein, the formation of PLA crystals in the PE and PE1MX membranes could contribute to enhanced mechanical strength of the polymeric membranes, which will benefit the use of the composite membrane under stressed conditions. Interestingly, the characteristic plane (104) of MAX phase was displayed in the XRD pattern of PE1MX membrane at 38.8° . This peak barely shifted from the XRD peak of pristine MAX phase at 38.9° (Fig. S2a). An insignificant XRD peak shift coupled with no new FTIR peaks formed (Fig. 4a) suggests that the MAX phase did not have strong interactions with the PLA matrix.

Fig. 5 represents stress-strain results of the PLA-based membranes, which can be used to describe the effect of increased PLA crystallinity on the mechanical properties of PE and PE1MX membranes. PLA, PE, and PE1MX membranes exhibited Young's moduli of 4.22 ± 0.33 , 21.91 ± 0.33 , and 6.77 ± 0.71 MPa, stress of 0.17 ± 0.00 , 0.31 ± 0.01 , and 0.33 ± 0.01 MPa, percentage strain of 14.61 ± 0.43 , 2.90 ± 0.22 , and 32.90 ± 1.11 %, and toughness of 1.84 ± 0.02 , 0.63 ± 0.06 , and 8.82 ± 0.67 MJ m⁻³, respectively. When compared to PLA membranes, PE and PE1MX membranes showed higher stresses and higher Young's moduli owing to the newly-formed PLA crystals from the presence of PEG (Fig. 4b). It was previously reported that the accumulation of

the filler particulates resulted in a plasticizing effect [42]. In this work, the stacking structure of the MAX phase resembled the agglomeration of the filler particles in the earlier work. The MAX phase particles were positioned between the polymer chains, which behaved as a plasticizer. Under these conditions, the PLA matrix could be softened with an observed lower Young's modulus of the PE1MX membrane. The mechanical properties of these PLA-based membranes can be related to the different morphologies of PLA (Fig. 1h), PE (Fig. 3a), and PE1MX (Fig. 3b). Based on Fig. 3d-f, the PE1MX membrane contained the finest fibers as compared to the PLA and PE membranes. These thin PLA fibers are able to entangle with each other and form strong polymeric fibrous networks that resist external tension. Due to the excellent mechanical properties of the MAX phase [23,43] and a high degree of PLA fiber entanglement, coupled with the presence of PEG-induced PLA crystals, the PE1MX membrane was accordingly tougher, able to undergo longer elongation, and thus more mechanically durable than the PLA and PE membranes.

Fig. 5. Mechanical properties of PLA, PE, and PE1MX membranes: (a) tensile stress-strain curves and (b) Young's modulus, percentage strain, stress, and toughness. For the statistical analysis in (b), the average values having different letters (a-c) are statistically different ($p < 0.05$).

The thermal properties of the PLA-based membranes were determined, and the results support the membrane mechanical behavior. DSC heating thermograms (Fig. 6a) and related thermal characteristics (Table 2) reveal that the PLA membrane is in an amorphous state (in line with XRD findings, Figure 4b), which showed a crystallization temperature (T_c) of 105.8 °C under heat treatment. The PE and PE1MX membranes showed broad peaks of pre-melt crystallization at ~130 °C upon being heated. The crystallization was not as evident as found in the PLA membrane since these PE and PE1MX membranes already contained PLA crystals (Fig. 4b) induced by the PEG presence. Membrane crystallinities (X_c) were different for PLA (17.1 %), PE (41.7 %), and PE1MX (38.7 %) membranes. The PE membranes accordingly showed evidently harder and more brittle mechanical behavior compared to the PLA and PE1MX membranes (Fig. 5a-b). The presence of PEG in the PLA membrane lowered the glass transition temperature (T_g) of PLA from 66.7 to 51.8 °C and the melting temperature (T_m) from 155.5 to 149.2 °C due to the plasticizing effect of PEG. More importantly, the T_g of PLA increased from 51.8 °C (PE membrane) to 53.4 °C (PE1MX membrane), reflecting the restriction of PLA chain mobility by the MAX phase because some portions of the MAX phase particles were embedded in the PLA fiber (Fig. 3c).

Fig. 6. Thermal characteristics of PLA-based membranes: (a) DSC first heating curves, (b) TGA thermograms, and (c) derivative weight curves related to (b). Inset in (b) shows thermal analysis in the temperature range of 30–225 °C.

Table 2 Thermal properties of PLA, PE, and PE1MX membranes investigated by DSC.

Membrane	T_g	T_c	ΔH_c	T_m	ΔH_m	X_c
	(°C)	(°C)	(J/g)	(°C)	(J/g)	(%)
PLA	66.7	105.8	32.8	155.5	48.7	17.1
PE	51.8	-	-	149.2	31.0	41.7
PE1MX	53.4	-	-	150.3	28.6	38.7

The thermal stability of PE and PE1MX membranes was studied to determine the effect of MAX phase in the fibrous membrane. Fig. 6b-c show that the temperature at 5 wt% weight loss ($T_{5\%}$) of PE and PE1MX membranes was 196.8 and 206.1 °C, respectively. The initial weight loss is attributed to the loss of moisture from the sample. Maximum thermal degradation rate of PE and PE1MX membranes was found at the maximum degradation temperature (T_{max}) of 356.5 and 334.7 °C, respectively. PE1MX membranes had lower T_{max} than PE membranes due to localized heat at the highly thermally conductive MAX phase, which is then transferred to the polymer fibers, causing membrane degradation at relatively lower temperature [23,35,43]. More importantly, both PE and PE1MX membranes were thermally stable up to ~190 °C, as indicated by the $T_{5\%}$ values, which is much higher than the operating temperature of the Cur-delivery membranes (skin temperature). The membranes also exhibit promise in their ability to withstand sterilization and high-temperature processing conditions. At the end of the TGA test (430 °C), there was no residue remaining for the PE membrane, whereas 4.26 % sample residue remained for the PE1MX membrane, since the MAX phase is resistant to high temperature [23].

3.4 Cytotoxicity studies of plasticized PLA (PE) and PLA/MAX phase (PE1MX) membranes

Direct and indirect *in vitro* methods were applied to comparatively determine cytotoxicity of the PE and PE1MX membranes for mouse fibroblast L929 cells (Fig. 7). These two samples were tested for their cytotoxicity to determine the effect of MAX phase presence in the PLA membranes on the toxicity to the cells. Fig. 7a shows that the cell viability of PE and PE1MX membranes was 80.0 ± 1.0 and 84.0 ± 2.2 % at 24 h, and 86.5 ± 1.0 and 89.3 ± 0.2 % at 72 h, respectively. It was therefore ascertained that the PE and PE1MX membranes were non-toxic to L929 cells after both 24 and 72 h, as indicated by the cell viability percentages over 70 %. SEM images (Fig. 7b) reveal that L929 cells proliferated on the fibrous surfaces of the PE and PE1MX membranes after 7 days. It was earlier reported that substrate hydrophilicity was an important factor promoting cell adhesion to the substrate [44], resulting in higher cell proliferation. In this work, electrospun membrane containing MAX phase was more hydrophilic than the membrane without MAX phase, as shown in Fig. 10a-b. Therefore, the PE1MX membrane showed higher cell proliferation compared to the PE membrane. Since the PLA fibers were smaller than the cell size, the cells maintained their somewhat spherical morphology while proliferating. The higher-resolution SEM images, however, revealed that the cells were still adherent to the membrane substrates, as highlighted red in Fig. S4a-b. Based on the low cytotoxicity of the PE and PE1MX membranes, they are promising for use as scaffolds in biomedical applications.

Fig. 7. Cytotoxicity investigation of PE and PE1MX membranes for L929 cells: (a) cell viability tested by a quantitative indirect method and (b) *in vitro* direct contact method shown by cell proliferation on the membranes at the beginning and after 7 days.

3.5 Characterization of Cur and Cur-MAX phase

Cur is a hydrophobic drug with spherical morphology (Fig. S3). The average Cur particle size in this work was measured as $0.614 \pm 0.319 \mu\text{m}$ (see Fig. 8a, $n = 50$). Fig. 8a shows Cur attachment on a MAX phase particle, indicating the promising use of MAX phase as Cur adsorbent and relevant releaser. EDS analysis of the MAX phase in the highlighted region (Spectrum 1) of Fig. 8a indicates the composition of MAX phase (Ti, Al, and C), shown as an EDS spectrum and tabulated as an inset in Fig. 8b. The immobilization of Cur particles on MAX phase was further investigated using XPS. In comparison to the XPS spectra of Cur and MAX phase (Fig. 8c), the XPS spectrum of Cur-MAX phase consists of Al 2p, C 1s, Ti 2p, and O 1s peaks, which corresponds to the compositional elements of MAX phase (Al, Ti, C) and Cur (C and O). High-resolution XPS scans of the Ti 2p region for the MAX phase (lower panel, Fig. 8d) display deconvoluted peaks at different binding energies for Ti in MAX phase (454.2 eV), Ti-C (458.3 eV), and TiO_2 (464.2 eV) [45,46]. For the Cur-MAX phase (higher panel, Fig. 8d), the three peaks

found in the MAX phase shifted towards higher binding energy for the Ti in MAX phase (455.4 eV), Ti-C (459.1 eV), and TiO₂ (464.9 eV), respectively. Since binding energy shifts are caused by changes in the chemical environment [47], the shifts found herein indicate that Ti in Cur-MAX phase was in a higher oxidation state compared to the Ti in MAX phase, reflecting some interactions between them [46]. The XPS findings therefore support the concept of Cur attachment on the surface of MAX phase.

Fig. 8. SEM image of (a) Cur attachment on MAX phase, and (b) EDS spectrum of the Spectrum 1 region highlighted in (a) with the elemental analysis results tabulated as an inset in (b). Scale bar in (a) is 10 μm . XPS analysis results of MAX phase, Cur, and Cur-MAX phase: (c) full-scan XPS spectra and (d) high-resolution XPS scans for Ti 2p region.

3.6 Characterization of Cur-loaded plasticized PLA (PEC) and PLA/MAX phase composite (PE1MXC) membranes

It has been demonstrated in Section 3.5 that Cur particles can attach onto the MAX phase surface, potentially benefiting Cur-delivery applications. To investigate this further, Cur-loaded electrospun membranes based on PLA have been explored. Although Cur loading into the polymer solution increased the viscosity of the electrospinning solution, fibrous morphologies of PEC (Fig. 9a) and PE1MXC (Fig. 9b) were still obtained. A comparison between the PEC (Fig. 9a) and PE1MXC (Fig. 9b) membranes illustrates that the presence of MAX phase aided formation of homogeneously fine polymer fibers due to overall increased solution conductivity as previously mentioned in Section 3.2.

Fig. 9. SEM images of (a) PEC and (b) PE1MXC membranes.

In addition to the morphology, membrane hydrophilicity (determined by water contact angle), WVTR, and porosity are important membrane properties for drug delivery applications. Fig. 10a shows time-dependent digital images of water drops on different membranes of PC, PEC, and PE1MXC. Water contact angles at every 0.5 s are depicted in Fig. 10b. Water contact angles

on PC membranes barely changed at $\sim 110^\circ$, indicating that the hydrophobicity of the PC membrane remained over 3 s. Therefore, the PC membrane was deemed unsuitable for Cur release in aqueous PBS solution. PEG was incorporated into the PLA membrane to increase the hydrophilicity of the membrane. It was found that the PEC membrane had water contact angles decreasing from $102.9 \pm 4.9^\circ$ to $86.9 \pm 9.4^\circ$ over 3 s, demonstrating enhanced membrane hydrophilicity following the addition of PEG. More importantly, the presence of hydrophilic MAX phase (1 phr) in the PE1MXC membrane contributed to a significant decrease in membrane hydrophobicity, as evidenced by the water contact angle of $86.2 \pm 16.7^\circ$ at the beginning (0 s) with the water drop disappearance within 3 s. Since PE1MXC membranes (Fig. 9b) comprised finer polymer fibers compared to PEC membranes (Fig. 9a), the porosity of the PE1MXC membrane was slightly higher than that of the PEC membrane, as shown later, enabling water droplets to penetrate through the PE1MXC membrane relatively more quickly (Fig. 10a-b).

Fig. 10. Time-dependent water contact angles on PC, PEC, and PE1MXC membranes: (a) chronological digital images showing water drops on each membrane surface and (b) water contact angle values at 0.5 s intervals. (c) WVTRs and (d) porosities of PEC and PE1MXC membranes.

WVTR (Fig. 10c) was investigated to determine the rate at which water vapor passed across each membrane. WVTR is an important indicator for the ability of the membrane to allow the wound underneath it to “breathe”. The WVTRs for PEC ($7291.0 \pm 414.4 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and PE1MXC ($7349.5 \pm 106.8 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) membranes were similar, being high enough for use as membranes in wound dressings. It has been previously reported that the WVTR for injured skin was $278.4 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$ [48]. Here, the porosities (Fig. 10d), which would allow water vapor to permeate, were not

significantly different for the PEC ($81.3 \pm 0.5 \%$) and PE1MXC ($84.5 \pm 1.0 \%$) membranes; thus it is unsurprising that these membranes exhibited similar WVTRs. In short, the presence of the MAX phase in the composite membrane (PE1MXC) did not suppress the porosity (and hence water vapor transmission) of the PEC membrane.

3.7 Antibacterial properties of Cur-loaded plasticized PLA (PEC) and PLA/MAX phase (PE1MXC) membranes

Antibacterial activity findings demonstrated that both PEC and PE1MXC membranes were able to lower the amount of *E. coli* (Fig. 11a) and *S. aureus* (Fig. 11b) when compared to the untreated control group. In particular, the PEC membrane exhibited obvious decreases in the amount of *E. coli* ($3.190 \log \text{CFU mL}^{-1} = 1548.82 \text{CFU mL}^{-1}$ at 168 h) and *S. aureus* ($3.953 \log \text{CFU mL}^{-1} = 8974.29 \text{CFU mL}^{-1}$ at 12 h). The PE1MXC membranes also exhibited an observed decrease in the amount of *E. coli* ($1.770 \log \text{CFU mL}^{-1} = 58.88 \text{CFU mL}^{-1}$ at 24 h) and *S. aureus* ($0.531 \log \text{CFU mL}^{-1} = 3.40 \text{CFU mL}^{-1}$ at 168 h). Based on these test results, the PE1MXC composite membranes could inhibit *E. coli* growth up to at least 168 h, while retarding the *S. aureus* growth at 168 h. The present findings agree with previous reports that Cur released from wound dressings of Cur-loaded ϵ -polycaprolactone/poly(vinyl alcohol) fibrous membranes [49] and patches of Cur-loaded poly(vinyl alcohol)/chitosan inhibited growth of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* [50]. The mechanisms of Cur in bacterial inhibition towards *E. coli* and *S. aureus* have been previously reported [51]. Briefly, sortase A enzyme of *S. aureus* was hindered by interacting with VAL-168, LEU-169, and GLN-172 sites of Cur. For *E. coli*, by impeding the synthesis of quorum sensing-dependent elements, bacterial activity was hindered. When these patches were tested on a rat wound, the wound healing performance of the patches was excellent due to the Cur delivery to

the skin. Herein, it is thus promising to apply the PE1MXC composite membrane as a candidate for topical use with Cur released to minimize the bacterial contamination.

Fig. 11. Antibacterial activities of PEC and PE1MXC membranes in comparison to untreated control for (a) *E. coli* and (b) *S. aureus* at different incubated times. For the statistical analysis, the average values having different letters (a-h) are statistically different ($p < 0.05$).

3.8 *In vitro* Cur release of Cur-loaded plasticized PLA (PEC) and PLA/MAX phase (PE1MXC) membranes

Fig. 12a illustrates the quantity of Cur released from different PEMXC composite membranes containing various MAX phase contents after 168 h, compared to the PEC membrane. For comparison, Cur release was also investigated for the Cur-loaded MAX phase with the release of 91.59 ± 1.10 %. Cur release tended to rise with increasing MAX phase loading content in the membranes and reached its maximum at MAX phase loading content of 1 phr, while leveling off at higher MAX phase contents (3 and 5 phr). The PE1MXC membrane was accordingly selected for further investigation for its Cur-release profile as a function of time and compared to that of the PEC membrane (Fig. 12b). Instead of using composite membranes with higher MAX phase

loadings (3 and 5 phr), it was found that a loading of 1 phr MAX phase was sufficient for maximum benefit. In particular, the PE1MX formulation was selected for further Cur loading. The 1 phr MAX phase contributed to a high Cur-release percentage of the PE1MXC membrane without sacrificing the low cytotoxic property of the PE1MX membrane (Fig. 7a-b). Higher MAX phase loadings could potentially lead to increased cytotoxicity and resultant cell death on the membrane scaffold. The PE1MX membrane developed in this work has a Cur-delivery performance comparable to other Cur-carrier materials previously reported, which showed a release amount of 53–80 % (Table 3). These materials are used for comparison because of their similarities in carrier form (membranes) and drug type (Cur), with a difference in the materials used to fabricate the drug carriers. The development made by the present work to the field is an application of MAX phase as a potential additive to polymeric carriers of Cur, which is commonly used in biomedical and pharmaceutical applications. Moreover, the MAX phase can be promisingly extended to other synthetic and naturally derived polymers in various forms of membranes, hydrogels, films, sponges, and monoliths.

Table 3 Cur delivery performance of Cur-carrier materials.

Material	Cumulative release	Reference
Electrospun poly(L-lactic acid) fiber mats	53 %	[3]
Poly(vinyl alcohol) nanofibers	73 %	[4]
Electrospun polycaprolactone/montmorillonite nanocomposites	80 %	[5]
Electrospun zein-silk fibroin-chitosan nanofibers	79 %	[6]
Poly(HEMA-MAPA) membranes	70 %	[52]
Cellulose acetate/polyvinylpyrrolidone fibrous materials	68 %	[53]
Electrospun PEG-plasticized PLA/MAX phase membranes	66.52%	This work

The PEC and PE1MXC membranes exhibited a similar biphasic release pattern, with an initial rapid release of Cur within the first 24 h, followed by a gradual and sustained release, maintaining the maximum amount of Cur release from 24 to 168 h. Looking at Cur release after 168 h (Fig. 12a-b), PEC membranes showed a lower Cur release (45.09 ± 3.27 %) compared to that (66.52 ± 4.43 %) of the PE1MXC membrane. Owing to the presence of MAX phase (1 phr) in the PE1MXC membrane, the enhancement in Cur release was equivalent to 47.53 %. The effect of MAX phase in promoting Cur release could be attributed to the Cur attachment on the MAX phase surface, as indicated in the SEM image (Fig. 8a) and the XPS results (Fig. 8d). Additionally, some portions of the MAX phase particles protruded out of the polymer fibers, as shown in Fig. 3c. With such MAX phase-fiber configuration, the Cur particles immobilized on the MAX surface were released faster than those embedded inside the polymer fibers in the case of PEC membranes.

Furthermore, the PE1MXC membrane had finer fibers (Fig. 9a-b) and a more porous structure (Fig. 10d) than the PEC membrane. As a result, the PE1MXC composite membrane allowed intermediate Cur dispersion to permeate out quickly [54].

Fig. 12. (a) Cur release performance of PEC and PEMXC membranes containing different MAX phase contents at 168 h, in comparison to Cur-loaded MAX phase (MX/Cur). (b) Cumulative Cur release profiles of PEC and PE1MXC membranes over 168 h. Cur release kinetic data of PEC and PE1MXC membranes, plotted with different kinetic models: (c) zero-order, (d) first-order, (e) Hixon-Crowell, (f) Kersmeyer-Peppas, and (g) Higuchi models. For the statistical analysis in (a), the average values having different letters (a-d) are statistically different ($p < 0.05$).

To analyze the Cur release kinetics of PEC and PE1MXC membranes, several kinetic models of zero-order (Fig. 12c), first-order (Fig. 12d), Hixon-Crowell (Fig. 12e), Kersmeyer-Peppas (Fig. 12f), and Higuchi (Fig. 12g) were adopted. After fitting the Cur release data with different types of kinetic models, it was found that the most appropriate model to describe Cur release from the PEC and PE1MXC membranes was the Higuchi model because of the relatively high R^2 values of 0.9720 (PEC) and 0.9939 (PE1MXC) compared to the R^2 values obtained using other models (Table 4). Based on the Higuchi model, the Cur release mechanism from these membranes is expected to involve the diffusion of Cur particles from polymeric matrices [54], as well as Cur detachment from MAX phase surface in the present work. Based on the R^2 of 0.9400 (PEC) and 0.9896 (PE1MXC) as shown in Fig. 12f, another possible Cur release mechanism could be the Korsmeyer–Peppas model. Calculated release exponent (n) values were 0.6977 (PEC) and 0.6670 (PE1MXC), corresponding to non-Fickian diffusion (anomalous transport) [55]. Cur release has also been attributed to other release mechanisms, such as polymer swelling and degradation together with Cur diffusion.

Table 4 Correlation coefficient (R^2) and release exponent (n) of different release kinetic models of PEC and PE1MXC membranes.

Kinetic model	R^2		n	
	PEC	PE1MXC	PEC	PE1MXC
Zero order	0.8812	0.9437	-	-
First order	0.6145	0.7347	-	-
Hixson-Crowell	0.7208	0.8256	-	-
Korsmeyer-Peppas	0.9400	0.9896	0.6977	0.6670
Higuchi	0.9720	0.9939	-	-

4. Conclusions

This article presents the successful use of MAX phase (Ti_3AlC_2) as a Cur-delivery performance enhancer with the demonstration of low cytotoxicity of PEG-plasticized PLA/MAX phase polymer composite membranes containing 1 phr MAX phase (PE1MX). In the presence of MAX phase in the electrospun composite membrane, fine polymer fibers were produced allowing for fiber entanglement and resultant higher mechanical toughness relative to plasticized PLA membranes. Viability of mouse fibroblast L929 cells for the composite membrane was >70 % under incubation times of 24 and 72 h with cell proliferation over 7 days, suggesting potential biomedical applications of the composite membrane. High WVTR ($\sim 7350 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$), high hydrophilicity (water contact angle of 0° within 3 s), high porosity ($\sim 85 \%$), and antibacterial properties against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (168 h incubation time) of the Cur-loaded composite membrane (PE1MXC) enables the possibility of using the composite membrane in, for example, topical wound dressing. Finally, the PE1MXC membrane offered higher cumulative Cur release ($\sim 66.52 \%$) over 168 h, when compared to the Cur-loaded plasticized PLA membrane (PEC, $\sim 45.09 \%$). The enhancement in Cur delivery is attributed to the Cur release from the large surface

area of MAX phase protruding from the polymer filbers, coupled with the relatively fine fibers of the composite membrane that possessed membrane high surface area for the release of Cur particles, as compared to those of the plasticized membrane (without MAX phase). The Cur release mechanism most closely follows Higuchi kinetic model, indicating diffusion of Cur particles from the polymer membrane as well as Cur release from the MAX phase surface.

As a polymer with low carbon footprint in accordance with sustainable development, PLA was successfully employed as a green polymer for the fabrication of fibrous membranes. This article also promisingly proposes MAX phase as an alternative to MXene for use as a performance enhancer of polymeric membranes in drug delivery applications.

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